

GHR SST
GROUP FOR HIGH RESOLUTION
SEA SURFACE TEMPERATURE

Feature Fidelity

Task Team

of the Group for High Resolution Sea Surface Temperature

Task Team Objectives

The Feature Fidelity task team was formed to address issues of uncertainty of satellite-derived SST fields in relation to the study of oceanographic features at mesoscale and smaller, i.e. $<O(100 \text{ km})$. Features such as currents, fronts, eddies, and gradients are defined by differences in SST over the spatial scale of interest. Critical to the study of these features is the uncertainty in the SST differences rather than the uncertainty in the absolute SST.

Major Achievements

The activities of this task team have been broken down into tasks:

- Task 1: Classification of types of problems contributing to uncertainties at different spatial scales
- Task 2: Identification of effects giving rise to these problems
- Task 3: Outline approaches to quantifying the uncertainties of interest

A report was provided in 2021: <https://zenodo.org/record/7263467#.Y5H7HHaZOhs>

The spatial scales associated with various categories of problems have been discussed within the task team:

Figure 1: Spatial Scales of SST Errors Associated with Cause. Credits: Peter Cornillon.

Upcoming Challenges

Two approaches will be investigated:

- Metrological approach: propagation of errors through the processing steps
- Determine uncertainty from the variance of the SST fields

A manuscript on the: “The Fidelity of Features in Satellite-Derived Sea Surface Temperature Field” with focus on issues related to the fidelity of SST features is in the pipeline. This would include instrument and retrieval-related issues:

1. Instrument-related issues:
 - Instrument noise.
 - Scanner geometry, e.g., The Bow-Tie Effect.
2. Retrieval-related issues:
 - Calibration.
 - Structure of the equation used for retrieval, e.g., spatially averaging the nonlinear term in a nonlinear algorithm vs not doing so.
 - Atmospheric contamination, e.g., the imprint of atmospheric phenomena on the SST field.
 - Classification errors, e.g., cloud-contaminated pixels flagged as clear or Front pixels flagged as bad.

Useful resources

Webpage: <https://www.ghrsst.org/about-ghrsst/task-teams/task-team-on-feature-resolution/>

Video report from GHRST23: <https://vimeo.com/showcase/9536986>

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/GHRST>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/ghrsst/>

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Who we are

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Interested in getting involved?

Please contact the chair and the co-chair!

About GHRST

This report has been edited by the GHRSSST project office.

The GHRSSST Project Office is funded by the European Union Copernicus Programme and is hosted by the Danish Meteorological Institute, Lyngbyvej 100, 2100 Copenhagen (DK)

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